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PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT IN ADULTHOOD

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Annotation: This article analyzes the psychological and social aspects of personality development during adulthood. In addition, it highlights the main characteristics of this period, the factors influencing development, the psychological challenges faced, and the role of education, family, and society in the process. Special attention is given to the importance of psychological support and social assistance systems in shaping a mature personality

Key words: period of adulthood, personality development, psychological stability, social adaptation, psychological changes, professional growth, emotional maturity, personal responsibility, life goals, development mechanisms

Introduction.

Each stage of human life is characterized by its own physical, psychological and social changes. Among them, the period of adulthood (i.e. the period of adulthood or puberty) is of particular importance in terms of the formation of a person's personal maturity, social activity and the ability to make independent decisions. During this period, a person faces issues such as self-awareness, setting goals, and shaping professional and family life. Personal development during adulthood includes not only complete biological formation, but also psychological and moral stabilization. At this stage, a person begins to acquire a certain social position in society through his interests, worldview, and attitude to life.

Methodological methods of the study. The following methodological approaches were used in this study: Observation method - the daily social and emotional activities of people of mature age were analyzed. Interview - in-depth conversations were conducted about the life experiences and psychological difficulties of the participants. Analysis and generalization - the collected data were summarized statistically and qualitatively.

Discussion. The period of adulthood is one of the most stable and active stages of human life in terms of biology and psychology. Usually this period includes the period from 20 to 40 years. During this period, a person determines his social status, is actively involved in professional activities, starts a family and begins to fulfill important social roles. At this stage, the person's outlook on life, value system and motivations are largely determined. During this period, the person defines his professional goals and works towards achieving them. Attitude to work, independence in choosing a profession, striving for professional self-development - all this plays an

important role during this period[1]. During this period, a person tries to fulfill social roles, take responsibility and strive for social stability. Relationships such as friendship, family, and parenthood are formed. Mature people strive to establish stable, deep relationships with those around them.

The period of adulthood is a developed stage of a person's ability to manage his own life, make decisions, understand himself and choose his own lifestyle. In this process, a person feels his own worth, understands his inner world and determines his life goals. Like any developmental process, certain psychological crises, internal conflicts, and problems related to life choices are observed during adulthood. Sometimes professional dissatisfaction, family disagreements, social pressure, and uncertainties in self-esteem lead a person to psychological stress. In such cases, the use of personal resources and the presence of a social support system are of great importance[2].

The development of a person during adulthood is one of the least studied problems in psychology. For example, psychoanalytic theories focus on personality anomalies and pathological variants. The norm is considered to be the absence of signs of illness. Another direction, representatives of humanistic psychology, absolutize famous personalities who have manifested their identity. N.A. Rybnikov in the 1920s called the field of youth psychology, which studies the laws of development of adults, acmeology [3]. This idea has led to the transformation of acmeology into an independent scientific discipline in the last 10 years, studying the mechanisms, laws and mechanisms of human development in adulthood. Acmeology studies the conditions, ways and methods of the formation of a person as an individual, as a talented subject of activity, as an individuality, as a parent, citizen, spouse, friend.

A.A. Bodalev noted that the peak of a mature person's development, that is, the phenomenon of acme as the peak of maturity, is a multidimensional state, variable and changeable, the peak is reached differently at different age periods. Observing the human life path is of great importance in preparing for the forms and content of the manifestation of the macroacme of human development of each age period (infancy, early childhood, school age, etc.). Studying the lives of famous people who left a great mark in science and culture, it is possible to observe the manifestation of microacme at each stage of life. Comparing acme in different people revealed that its manifestation can be local (within one activity) and wide (in many areas) [4].

Results. The period of maturity is a period of formation of a person as an independent, stable and responsible person. During this period, the psychological characteristics of the individual, in particular, self-awareness, motivation, stability and emotional maturity, are manifested at a high level. Among the important factors influencing development are the family, society, the educational system, the professional environment and psychological support services. An integrated approach

is necessary to eliminate psychological problems encountered during adulthood: this includes prevention, counseling and social support. The social and professional success of a person, life satisfaction and psychological health largely depend on the level of development during this period.

Conclusion. Based on the above considerations, the following conclusion was made: The period of adulthood is the most important stage in the process of full-fledged formation of a person, self-awareness, setting life goals and achieving them. During this period, a person establishes his professional, family, social and personal life, strives to make independent decisions regarding his life, feel responsible and actively participate in society. Also, during this period, psychological stability, emotional balance, and the ability to manage social relationships are formed at a high level. However, sometimes this process can be negatively affected by various factors - social pressure, family problems, professional uncertainty, or internal conflicts. Therefore, an integrated approach to the development of a person during this period is necessary.

Suggestions. Based on the content of the study, the following suggestions were put forward:

- Strengthening psychological support services. Counseling centers, psychological training, and practical exercises on stress management should be organized for adults;

- Improving the career guidance system. In order to increase professional satisfaction and opportunities for self-realization, special programs on career guidance and personal planning should be developed in educational institutions;

- Creating a social support environment. It is necessary to create a healthy environment in the family, society, and workplace that encourages and supports the individual mentally;

- Introducing programs aimed at personal development. Programs should be developed for adults to develop life skills, decision-making, and communication skills.

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